

The number and territorial settlement of Ukrainians in Moldova at the beginning of the XXI century

PhD Victor COJUHARI,
Institute of Cultural Heritage

After Moldova gained independence, the number of Ukrainians (as well as the total population) decreased significantly.

If in the previous period the number of Ukrainians had grown continuously, in 1979 – 560,679 (14.2%), 1989 – 600,366 (13.8%), then after 1991 their number began to noticeably decline. In 2004, there were already 442,475 people (in the territory controlled by the central authorities – 282,406 (8.4%), in the territory of the unrecognized Transnistrian Moldovan Republic (TMR) – 160,069 (28.82%). In 2014 – 181,035 (6.6%) This situation is largely due to migration.

By regions, the Ukrainian population is traditionally densely settled in the northern region of the territory controlled by the central authorities, and in the territory of the unrecognized TMR. Among the northern regions, the largest numbers of Ukrainians living in them demonstrate: Bălți – 30,288 (23.74%), Briceni region – 19,939 (25.55%), Dondiușeni region – 5,893 (12.69%), Drochia region – 9,849 (11.31%), Edineți region – 16,084 (19.76%), Fălești region – 10,711 (11.86%), Glodeni region – 11,918 (19.55%), Ocnița region – 17,351 (30.70%), Rîșcani region – 15,632 (22.51%). In other areas of the right bank, Ukrainians make up less than 10%.

In the unrecognized TMR, the distribution is as follows: Tiraspol – 52,278 (33.07%), Benderi – 17,348 (17.88%), Camenca region – 11,610 (42.55%), Rîbnița region – 37,554 (45.41%), Dubăsari region – 10,594 (28.84%), Grigoriopol region – 8,333 (17.36%), Slobozia region – 19,872 (22.91%).

The largest number of Ukrainians in these areas is due to historical events. Since the Middle Ages, in numerous waves, Ukrainians from Bukovina and Podolia migrated to the north of the modern Republic of Moldova.

The territory of the unrecognized TMR was also a part of Ukraine since the Middle Ages until 1940. Therefore, Ukrainians have lived here for many centuries.